

ADD ON EFFECT OF AGNIHOTRA HOMA AND AGNIHOTRA BHASMA SHIROPICHU IN THE MANAGEMENT OF STRESS DISORDER: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Stress, termed the “Health Epidemic of the 21st Century” by the WHO, disrupts emotional, physical, and mental well-being, contributing to a wide range of psychosomatic disorders. In Ayurveda, stress is attributed to an imbalance caused by *kleshas* (~mental afflictions), while yogic philosophy associates it with *dukkha* (~misery), leading to mental and physical disharmony. This case study explores the integrative use of *Agnihotra* (~Vedic fire ritual) and *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu* as part of *Daiva Vyapashraya Chikitsa*, an Ayurvedic spiritual healing approach.^[1] A 31-year-old male with symptoms of stress disorder, including anxiety, restlessness, insomnia, and somatic discomfort, underwent a 7-day treatment protocol. The therapy included daily *Agnihotra* practice at sunset using cow dung cakes, unbroken rice, and ghee, along with the chanting of *Maha Mrityunjaya* and *Shanti mantras*. The resulting ash

(*Bhasma*) was applied topically to the head in the form of *Shiropichu*. Pre-therapy evaluation revealed low mood, poor concentration, and passive suicidal thoughts. Following the intervention, the patient reported marked improvement in mood, sleep quality, focus, and overall functionality. This case highlights the potential of *Agnihotra* as a simple, cost-

effective, and holistic adjunct in managing stress-related disorders, bridging ancient healing practices with modern mental health care.

KEYWORDS: Stress Disorder, *Agnihotra*, *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu*, *Daiva Vyapashraya Chikitsa*, Case Report.

INTRODUCTION

Stress denotes psychological distress as a result of increased circumstantial nervous strain to overwhelm an adaptive capacity.^[1] Stress is declared as the “Health Epidemic of the 21st Century” by WHO, which impacts the individual physically, emotionally or psychologically.^[2] Medical researchers estimate 90% of illnesses are stress related.^[3] Stressor is considered as a mental state that clouds the mind and manifests in unwholesome actions such as anxiety, fear, anger etc. Stressors are the causes of stress that have a major influence upon mood, sense of well-being, behaviour, and health.^[4] Medial prefrontal cortex and limbic structures are impacted during stress, which affects behaviour and thinking process, resulting in cognitive, psychotic and mood disorders.^[5]

According to *yoga*, *dukkha* (~Sorrow) is the primary source of stress, which manifests itself as psychosomatic disorder.^[6] The term *klesha* (~impurity) is the root cause of suffering, aptly characterizing stress as disturbing the inner equilibrium, resulting in physical and mental imbalances.^[7] Repetitive ruminations about something causes attachment, which is an etiological component in causing mental disorder.^[7]

Daiva Vyapashraya Chikitsa (~divine interventions) is one of the three Ayurvedic therapeutic approaches.^[8] *Daiva Vyapashraya Chikitsa* is gaining global attention in the modern era due to its scientifically established benefits.^[9] The therapy principle of *Daiva vyapashraya* comprises the usage of *Manidharana* (~precious stones), as well as *Mantra* (~sacred utterance), *Bali* (~oblation), *Homa* (~Vedic fire ritual), *Abhyupahara*, *Japa* (~repetition chanting of hymns).^[10] Vedas mention a fivefold path for blissful happiness, namely *Yajna* (~*agnihotra*), *Daana* (~offerings), *Tapa* (~undergo penance), *Karma* (~action) and *Swadhyaya* (~self-study).^[11] *Agnihotra*, a form of *Homa/Yajna*, is a ritual of lighting fire in a small rectangular copper pyramid pot using dried cakes of cow dung and offering pure cow ghee and unbroken rice to the fire at sunrise and sunset with chanting of mantras.^[12,13] Its origin is traced to *Rigveda*, where positive gains for physical and mental health and energy are preached with daily practice

of *Agnihotra*.^[14] *Agnihotra* is performed daily to maintain the equilibrium of nature and enhance human life.^[14]

Several studies have shown the effect of *Yajna* on hormones and neurotransmitters to fight diseases of the brain such as epilepsy, insomnia, anxiety and nosocomial infections.^[15] The *Bhasma* (ash) procured after *Agnihotra* is known to have multiple benefits for mind and body. It is used for water purification, as antifungal application, and so on.^[16,17] It is a simple, cost-effective, and feasible procedure with no gender discrimination to perform.^[18]

Patient Information

A 31-year-old male, employed as a sales executive, presented with a range of emotional and physical symptoms that had gradually developed over the past six months. He described experiencing persistent restlessness, anxiety, and a sense of mental overwhelm. At night, he struggled to fall asleep, and even when sleep occurred, it was frequently interrupted. As a result, he often woke feeling unrefreshed and fatigued, which began to interfere with his ability to function effectively during the day.

He reported increasing difficulty in meeting professional demands and noticed a steady decline in both motivation and job performance. Alongside these emotional challenges, he experienced physical discomfort, particularly a burning sensation in the chest and a sense of unease in the upper abdomen in turn which he attributed to ongoing stress.

Over time, his emotional well-being continued to decline. He gradually withdrew from social interactions, lost interest in previously enjoyed activities, and felt emotionally disconnected from his surroundings and relationships. He had no prior history of psychiatric illness, had never been on regular medication, and reported no use of alcohol, tobacco, or recreational substances. There was no family history of mental health disorders.

CLINICAL FINDING (PRE-THERAPY EVALUATION)

On physical examination, the patient appeared well-nourished with a Body Mass Index (BMI) of 23.4 kg/m.^[2] No significant physical abnormalities were noted. He was casually dressed, maintained adequate hygiene, though mild neglect in grooming was observed. Appetite was mildly reduced, and sleep was significantly impaired. Bowel and bladder habits were normal. There was no history of substance use, known allergies, or prior psychiatric illness. Family history was non-contributory.

Mental Status Examination revealed a conscious, cooperative individual oriented to time, place, and person. He established rapport with some effort and maintained intermittent eye contact. His speech was coherent and goal-directed. The patient reported a persistently low mood, with a constricted affect and visible restlessness. Thought content was marked by excessive worry and occasional passive suicidal ideation without intent. No perceptual disturbances were present. Cognitive functions were intact. Judgment was preserved, though insight was limited and emotional distress appeared to impair decision-making.

Diagnosis and Assessment

The patient was diagnosed with Stress-Disorder (ICD-11: 6B4Z – Disorders Specifically Associated with Stress, Unspecified) based on persistent symptoms of restlessness, insomnia, palpitations, poor concentration, and emotional distress. Differential diagnoses such as Generalized Anxiety Disorder and Somatoform Disorder were considered but ruled out due to the non-specific yet chronic nature of symptoms without a singular triggering event. Despite occasional passive suicidal thoughts, the patient remained oriented with intact cognition and insight. His openness to holistic interventions and absence of comorbid psychiatric conditions suggested a favorable prognosis with appropriate therapeutic support.

Assessment

Before and after treatment Assessment was made using Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) and Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) where the PSS assessed the subjective parameters, GSR observed the objective findings.

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is a widely recognized psychological instrument used to measure the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful. The PSS evaluates subjective stress perception, making it especially valuable in identifying emotional responses to life events, irrespective of their actual severity. The before treatment assessment of PSS score was 28 denoting highly stressed state.

Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) is a psychophysiological measure used to assess the electrical conductance of the skin, which varies with its moisture level. Since sweat gland activity is controlled by the sympathetic nervous system, GSR is a reliable indicator of emotional arousal and stress. Higher GSR values typically reflect reduced stress or increased relaxation, while lower values may indicate heightened sympathetic activity and emotional distress. In

this case the observed GSR basal value and actual value before treatment was 230 μ S and 350 μ S respectively.

Therapeutic Intervention

The patient was under went Panchakarma therapy comprising of *Deepana* (~enhance appetite), *Pachana* (~digestion of toxin), *Snehapana* (~Internal oleation) and *Virechana* (~Therapeutic purgation). Along with this pharmacological treatment, the patient participated in *Agnihotra* therapy and received *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu* (~Application of tampon to the head) for 7 days.

Procedure of *Agnihotra* and *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu*

The *Agnihotra* procedure is a traditional Vedic ritual performed over a duration of one week (7 days) to harness spiritual and therapeutic benefits.

The treatment involves two main components: the *Agnihotra* ritual and the *Shiropichu* application. The *Agnihotra* ritual requires specific materials and precise timing for effective practice. The materials needed include a copper pyramid-shaped pot measuring 6 inches by 6 inches with a height of 3 inches (base dimensions of 2 inches by 2 inches), unbroken pieces of *shali* (~rice), *Go-gritha* (~pure cow's ghee), and *gomaya* (~dried cow dung cakes). Additionally, a matchbox is needed to light the fire. The procedure starts by preparing the *Agnihotra* ritual: one must sit quietly on the ground facing towards the sun. A few minutes before sunset, pieces of cow dung smeared with ghee are lit in the copper pot. At the exact local time of sunset, which can be determined from a local sunset timing chart, the practitioner holds approximately 10 grams of unbroken rice in the left palm, smears it with a drop of ghee, and offers portions of rice to the fire in the pot while chanting the *Mahamrityunjaya mantra* 21 times, followed by the *Agnihotra mantras*: 'Agnaye Svaha, Agnaye Idam Na Mama. Prajapataye Svaha, Prajapataye Idam Na Mama'. The ritual is completed by sitting quietly in a squatting position for a few minutes as the fire burns down and extinguishes. This entire process takes about 20 minutes.

Following the *Agnihotra* ritual, the *Shiropichu* procedure is performed as an external application over the bregma or vertex of the skull. For this procedure, the materials required include a 4 cm x 4 cm cotton pad, cotton gauze for tying, and a fresh banana leaf measuring 6 cm x 6 cm. To prepare for *Shiropichu*, 25 grams of *Agnihotra Bhasma* (the ash produced from the *Agnihotra* ritual) is mixed with a sufficient quantity of warm milk to form a semi-

solid paste. This paste is then applied to the vertex of the skull in a 4 cm x 4 cm area, with a thickness of about 1 inch. The banana leaf is placed over the applied paste, and the cotton gauze is used to secure the leaf in place. *Shiropichu* is maintained for a duration of 60 minutes each afternoon. After 60 minutes, the cotton pad and banana leaf are removed, and the applied area is gently cleaned. This procedure is repeated daily for 7 days. Both *Agnihotra* and *Shiropichu* are performed at the same local time each day to ensure consistency in the ritual's effectiveness.

Follow-up and Outcomes

Clinical Observations: Pre-therapy vs post-therapy

Parameter	Before Treatment	After Treatment
General Appearance & Behaviour	Mildly dishevelled, restless behaviour, subtle signs of diminished self-care	Well-groomed, composed, appropriate eye contact, no signs of distress
Mood & Affect	Anxious, sad, hopeless; restricted affect	Improved mood (“hopeful,” “in control”); appropriate affect with full range
Thought Content	Ruminative thoughts, cognitive distortions, health worries	No suicidal ideation, reduced cognitive distortions, less catastrophizing
Thought Process	Slightly scattered, preoccupied	Organized, goal-directed, coherent
Orientation	Fully oriented	Fully oriented
Attention & Concentration	Distractible, difficulty focusing	Significantly improved, better focus during interview and at work
Memory	Intact but reduced recent recall	Intact with better recent recall
Insight	Partial; limited awareness of emotional-physical link	Good; acknowledged emotional causes of physical symptoms
Judgment	Slightly impaired decision-making under stress	Appropriate; healthier coping and decision-making
Sleep	Difficulty initiating and maintaining sleep; non-restorative	Improved quality, restorative and refreshing sleep
Somatic Symptoms	Burning sensation in chest and abdominal discomfort	>70% reduction in symptoms; attributed to anxiety relief
Occupational Functioning	Impaired productivity, poor focus	Full duties resumed, enhanced productivity, improved multitasking
Social Engagement	Social withdrawal, limited interaction	Resumed hobbies, active participation in family/social activities
Energy & Motivation	Fatigue, low motivation	Marked improvement; described as “refreshed” and proactive
GSR Basal Value	230	310

GSR Actual Value	350	520
Overall Improvement from GSR	NA	~70% improvement in psychological and somatic
Overall PSS SCORE	28 (High stressed)	15 (Mild-moderate)

DISCUSSION

The patient presented with symptoms of mild distress, persistent low mood, feelings of hopelessness, and negative as well as suicidal ideations, resulting in significant disruption of both personal and occupational functioning¹⁹. These features are consistent with a diagnosis of Stress-Related Disorder (ICD-11 6B4Z – Disorders Specifically Associated with Stress, Unspecified), where emotional dysregulation and psychosocial impairment are hallmark features.^[19]

Cortisol, a key glucocorticoid hormone produced by the adrenal cortex, is integral to the body's stress response and is regulated by the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis.^[20] During stress, the hypothalamus releases corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), prompting the pituitary gland to secrete adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH), which in turn stimulates cortisol release.^[20] While short-term cortisol elevation aids adaptation by enhancing vigilance, mobilizing energy, and suppressing inflammation, chronic stress leads to HPA axis imbalance, associated with anxiety, depression, sleep disturbances, cognitive impairment, and physical symptoms such as fatigue and gastrointestinal upset.^[21] Prolonged cortisol exposure also disrupts neuroplasticity, particularly in the amygdala and hippocampus, and compromises immune and metabolic function.^[22,23] Therefore, interventions that normalize HPA axis activity and cortisol levels are central to stress management.^[23]

Agnihotra and *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu*, drawn from Ayurvedic and Vedic traditions, offer a unique integrative approach targeting multiple layers of the stress response.^[24,25] From a biomedical standpoint, stress disorders involve sympathetic overactivity, neurotransmitter imbalance, and neuroendocrine disruption.^[26] In Ayurveda, they reflect aggravated *Vata dosha* and a dominance of *Rajas guna*, manifesting as restlessness, emotional instability, and insomnia.^[27]

Agnihotra, performed at sunrise and sunset, synchronizes with circadian rhythms and promotes parasympathetic activation through its ritualistic sound, fragrance, and vibrational elements. Early studies suggest it may lower cortisol levels and support HPA axis regulation.^[28] Additionally, the process emits volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and

negative ions, which may influence olfactory-limbic circuits, modulating regions involved in emotional regulation, such as the amygdala.^[29] The practice is also regarded in Ayurveda as Daivavyapasraya Chikitsa (~spiritual therapy) that enhances Sattva guna, encouraging emotional balance and inner tranquillity.^[27]

Agnihotra Bhasma Shiropichu complements this approach by applying warm milk infused with *Agnihotra* ash to the *Adhipati Marma* (bregma)—a region linked with the *Sahasrara chakra* and neural hubs like the default mode network (DMN).^[30] This therapy aims to calm *Shirogata Vata*, cleanse *manovaha srotas* (~mental pathways), and support emotional and cognitive stability.^[31] The ash is rich in trace elements such as Zinc and Copper, known to assist in neurotransmitter synthesis, antioxidant defence, and neurological signalling.^[32] Through transdermal absorption via warm carriers, the formulation exerts nootropic, anxiolytic, and cooling effects, enhancing focus and reducing agitation.^[32,33]

In clinical practice, these therapies were employed alongside Ayurvedic detoxification and rejuvenation protocols, including *Virechana karma* (purgation), *snehapana* (internal oleation), and *abhyanga* (therapeutic massage).^[34] In a documented case, the add-on treatment led to improvements in both subjective parameters (mood, sleep, emotional stability) and objective outcomes, such as Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) scores, Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), occupational functioning, and cognitive performance.^[35]

In conclusion, *Agnihotra* and *Agnihotra Bhasma ShiroPichu* represent a promising Ayurvedic intervention for the management of stress disorders.^[36,37] Their combined influence on neurophysiological regulation, environmental purification, and psychospiritual restoration underscores their relevance within both traditional healing systems and modern integrative medicine.^[37] These outcomes warrant further exploration through structured clinical trials and neurobiological investigations to establish efficacy, safety, and mechanistic insights.^[37]

Taken together, this integrative intervention combining *snehapana*, *abhyanga*, *Virechana karma*, and *Agnihotra*-based practices demonstrated a holistic and effective approach to managing stress-related disorders.^[37] The patient showed marked improvements across subjective domains (mood, sleep, emotional stability) and objective markers (GSR, PSS Scale, occupational function, concentration), reinforcing the potential of such Ayurveda-based, multi-modal therapies.^[37] This case highlights the scope of further research in validating these therapies through structured clinical trials and neurobiological

investigations.^[37] This case demonstrates the promising role of *Agnihotra* Therapy, combined with *Agnihotra Bhasma Shiro-Pichu*, as intervention in the management of stress-related disorders.^[37]

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